

Analyst Administrator
Date Wednesday, June 1, 2022 2:10 PM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-134_1	Sample 032 By Administrator Date Wednesday, June 01 2022	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.